

SIGMUND FREUD AND THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PSYCHOANALYSIS AND SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the topic involving the psychoanalysis-science relationship. Its scientific relevance lies in the dimension of academic discussion, which shows the advances and everything that Psychoanalysis has promoted in terms of scientific discoveries, influencing thinking in all segments of the human and social sciences. Its social relevance lies in clarifying to the general public that it is not a science but a technique that, applied to an object, achieves great success in solving nervous problems. This is a bibliographical, factual, analytical, interpretative research, based on technical knowledge. Science tends to reduce everything to the individual and the simple, so that it can study each case in isolation, while Psychoanalysis, even when dealing with isolated individuals, cannot dissociate all the elements of the human, having to carry out their interpretation from a set of always interconnected data. Freud knew this very well and, as much as he fought to have his technique recognized as a science, we have to interpret this concept in the Master's thinking, which was something very specific in relation to his practice. When we think about approaching the theme of the psychoanalysis-science relationship, it becomes very complex, because given the fact that its object of work is not palpable and the subject possessing this object is volatile to temporal and spatial action, what Natural sciences call it confrontation with data, it does not apply to Psychoanalysis. It is a technique that, when applied in a correct, organized, systematic way, produces excellent therapeutic healing results and these, once compiled in the records, serves as guidance guides, enabling a broad understanding of the social object with which the health sciences are concerned social character, which is the human being.

Keywords: Sigmund Freud; Psychoanalysis; Science; Psychoanalysis-Science Relationship.

INTRODUCTION

Psychoanalysis is an *art*, understood as a *technique*, which can be applied to psychological, intellectual, and cognitive life, or even as a way of explaining behaviors that escape the normal understanding of things in everyday life, being restricted to the singularities of individual-unconscious life. Its specific characteristic as a technique of analysis and

existential interpretation has allowed it to be and/or could be applied to various fields of human activity, such as cinema, theater, literature, history, biographies of controversial characters, economics, advertising, *marketing* and *merchandising techniques*, clinical treatments of some nervous diseases such as depression, obsessive-compulsive disorder, neuroses, and it has even ended up being adopted as an important aid in pedagogical practice.

When one thinks about approaching the subject of the relationship between psychoanalysis and science, it becomes very complex, because given the fact that its object of work is not tangible and the subject possessing this object is fickle to temporal and spatial action, what the natural sciences call confrontation with data cannot be applied to psychoanalysis, because, although some elements addressed in it are factual, the experiments cannot be repeated, and this places it in a delicate position when referring to it as a science. On the other hand, denying all the advances provided by psychoanalytic studies to the fields of other sciences is to place it outside a scientific scope that would be much less powerful without its formal collaboration. Many fields of human knowledge ended up being directly impacted by the technique developed by Freud, opening paths for studies of various natures. Sigmund Freud fought throughout his life for Psychoanalysis to be recognized as an autonomous science and it can be said that he achieved his goal, because even though he faced several obstacles, one cannot deny the knowledge produced and discovered from his contribution and application to the phenomena that permeate human existence.

When Michel Foucault (1926-1984) raises the question of the scientificity that Psychoanalysis so longs for, he makes a reference to knowledge-power, claiming that its authority would no longer be guided by the effectiveness of the technique as such, to occupy a space of social consensus in relation to what is known and what is said and how much this knowledge-saying would be questioned and/or accepted by scientific communities, categorizing that it would become a science determined by paradigms and consensus and, its intellectual greatness lies in the phenomenological dissent that surrounds it, since it is a technique; therefore, it has an action of an empirical nature, and the result cannot be determined or presumed, *a priori*; at most, conjectures are constructed that may prove to be feasible, plausible or refutable. In this sense, Foucault's complaint is that this desire for scientism in relation to Psychoanalysis is a euphemism, a way of achieving power for power's sake and not through real action on an object and a specific field of systematic studies.

For Martin Heidegger (1889-1976), what characterizes the essence of technology is *technology in motion*. With this idea, he inaugurates a new notion of scientific accuracy, if that is how it can be referred to, because as he himself puts it, the study that focuses on empirically

linked phenomena and the spirit cannot be measured with the same yardstick as the exact sciences, in which there is a greater possibility of working under quantitative numerical guidance. At the time it was put forward and questioned, this represented both an advance and a surprise, starting with the fact that there were no evaluation instruments that could provide security to opponents. However, this cannot be a *conditio sine qua non* for a technique whose effectiveness is questioned to be execrated and excluded from academic circles, not being treated as a science that in its own way has its methodological and scientific rigor, these being some of the essential elements to characterize a science as such.

Sigmund's interest and desire in placing the technique he developed on the list of sciences was to make Psychoanalysis an object of academic study, even academic, with a chair in universities and, perhaps, as a course to be undertaken, along the same lines as Medicine and Philosophy. At the same time that he fought for this, he feared that, once in the hands of scientists, long removed from empirical experience, it would become rigid and condemned to an eternal state of repetition of theories without causal connection and without the minimum conditions to explain objective reality. Therefore, Freud's stance towards Psychoanalysis as a science was a reason for questioning even among his followers and disciples; notably, because the Master's stance in relation to his investigations demonstrated a dedication to empirical research as a way of discovering the causes of phenomena based on the individual experiences of each patient and how they processed and expressed them.

In addition to all this, it was necessary to analyze how the manifestation of repressed traumas affected the life of each individual, causing losses in their production and conditions of existential autonomy. This situation is something that cannot be standardized for academic purposes, much less generalized, demanding specific investigations, attentive to singularities and details that ordinary sciences do not address with the same care, because they are stagnant and, at times, stuck in redundant paradigms. Thus, it is clear that the relationship between Psychoanalysis and Science is very complex and represents a challenging issue that there is no absolute interest in solving, because this would represent losses for the former that would directly impact the latter.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PSYCHOANALYSIS AND SCIENCE

Relating psychoanalysis to the term science, in its strict sense, is a problem that has been around for centuries, but it cannot be ignored at the level of thought, because Freud's technique has reached spaces that could never have been reached were it not for its broad capacity to

introduce concepts into less tangible fields. Even so, thinking of it as a science may be audacious, due to the lack of an axis that allows for the comparison of results from the application of its principles to different objects, in different situations. However, Thomas S. Kuhn describes science as “research firmly based on one or more past scientific achievements exposed and reported in elementary or advanced scientific manuals” (KUHN, 1970, p. 101), which sets a precedent for it to be included in the list of sciences, if we understand that, at this point, the scientific reports and achievements of various psychoanalysts already make up the technical manuals in various fields of academic-scientific knowledge.

However,

It is necessary to clearly establish what the term Science, as an epistemological category, designates. From a rigorous perspective, Science is understood as the mode of knowledge production that, following the methodological parameters established by Galileo and interpreted by Descartes' discursive architecture, is characterized by: a) stripping away the sensitive or psychic qualities of the object that is being known; b) use of language stripped of comprehensible meanings shared by common knowledge in the formulation of theoretical discourse; c) strict adherence to the principle of contingency and universality, according to which each and every element to be studied could be infinitely different from what it is, with nothing previously obliging it to be as it is, and it is precisely up to science to clarify the ways in which it came to be as it is (ALBERTI and ELIA, 2008, p. 784).

When Psychoanalysis adopts the unconscious as its object of systematic study, Freud's idea was probably to follow the canonical scientific rules presented above by the authors. And many things can be subject to the rule, because Freudian thought followed a rigorous scheme of categorization of its object and even though Psychoanalysis has come to be interpreted as a technique, it assumes, at the same time, a line of studies that explores the object, bringing it to the field of semantics, from which it cannot be seen as detached, giving it scientific objectivity.

Problems arise in understanding psychoanalysis as a science because of the judgment that its field of exploration is nervous diseases and that these behave differently in each individual, varying singularly from case to case, and even from culture to culture. However, Freud emphasizes in several passages of his vast work that many phenomena studied and discovered through the application of his technique have a universal character; therefore, there is an element that does not advocate in favor of it, but that, paradoxically, does not advocate against it, because if a certain event occurs in all cultures, regardless of their historical background, it means that the analysis technique can be applied in all these cultures where it occurs and the results must be analyzed seeking maximum neutrality and technical-scientific competence, knowledge of the spatial-cultural environment and having as an object of

comparison, a certain parameter of epistemological confrontation. Once these procedures are followed, academic rigor is applied to the technique and, therefore, what would invalidate it as a science?

Alberti and Elia (2008) would say that all these elements and research performance mentioned

They characterize the hypothetical-deductive method created by Galileo, of which verification is the last stage, and it is to this lineage that Freud directly affiliates himself, without ambiguities and without other discursive mediations. Psychoanalysis, in this sense, is strictly derived from the inaugural method of modern science, and if it does not remain in the field of science, it is because it operates a radical subversion in this method, through which it introduces into the scene (hence the so-called Other scene, that of the unconscious), precisely that which the discourse of science, being a-semantic, universal and contingent, introduced, but, in the same blow, expelled from its operational field: the subject (and not man). Psychoanalysis operates with the subject, the same as science, which, however, does not operate on it (ALBERTI and ELIA, 2008, p. 784).

It can be understood from this explanation that Psychoanalysis seeks what is inside man, that which is not revealed by open observation and is not even of interest to standardized sciences, which is the discourse that is found in the most fundamental bases of the human *psyche*. However, none of this is tangible nor can it be measured or replicated, thus allowing a validation of the procedure and the responses. This condition, quite unique to Psychoanalysis, already places it on the margins of the sciences, which are governed by experimental means, in which mathematics and statistics can be used to determine their degree of precision.

This condition of the hard sciences is a factor that distances and makes it difficult, if not impossible, to treat Psychoanalysis as a science in itself. J. Lacan tries to create a link in which, hypothetically, such a situation would be possible, without, however, pointing out an adequate solution. “For Lacan then, bringing psychoanalysis closer to the sciences that admit conjecture, such as logic and mathematics, among others already mentioned, has the consequence of deepening, from the first hour of its teaching and with the utmost rigor, the discussion about the relations of Psychoanalysis with Science” (ALBERTI and ELIA, 2008, p. 796).

Rigor must exist in any circumstance involving *Phonésis* and *episteme*, and this is what involves the analytical process, since the search takes place in the field of the patient finding the strength (wisdom) to confront and know how to deal, in an appropriate manner, with what he will come to know, as the analyst advances in the therapeutic treatment and the truths are exposed, through interpretation. Here, we draw a parallel with Jaspers (1991) that it is through interpretation that knowledge emerges, that is, this is the product or consequence of that. And,

once again, we reach a point that is difficult to understand, because neither the analyst nor the patient is able to determine, at least, what will be exposed and what type of knowledge this may become. Therefore, taking this bias of understanding, there is no way for Psychoanalysis to be treated as a science. “For Freud, on the contrary, the affinity between psychoanalysis and the natural sciences always seemed evident and beyond any doubt” (SIMANKE, 2009, p. 225).

It can be inferred from this quote that, in Freud's view, because he used a biological structure as a way of analyzing human nature, this already characterized his condition as a science that would act in the same style, and could receive the same *status quo*. However, it is not known how he could reach such an understanding, because the object with which he worked was not new, but the way he communicated with it and the analyses directed at it did not leave many epistemological support guidelines that would guarantee a safe condition of validation. The only notion we can have of this attitude of the Master of Vienna is that he wanted to place his technique at a level that would be respected as something serious, not being subject to being inserted, by his adversaries, into the role of charlatanism.

The path followed by Freud, with the purpose of supporting Psychoanalysis as a science, on the same level as the natural sciences, is remarkable and worthy of respect, but it is not sufficient to guarantee such *status*, because the object with which one deals is very fickle and unstable and even worse is the situation that when confronted with the truth, the patient does not always support it and seeks ways to evade it, creating situations of ambiguity and confrontation, which leads to false interpretations, by those who do not have an adequate level of knowledge about how the human brain works, and even more so that of a neurotic, always in constant conflict.

If we take the case by method, the objective description of the process, the results and the entire procedure of analysis and interpretation, we have a science in the most objective sense; however, when we follow the Cartesian approach of validating scientific action, which is, in fact, what proves a phenomenon as true or false, we come up against this issue in relation to Psychoanalysis. We cannot focus on the fact of the universality of a given phenomenon, which is the object of study of a technique, in order to guarantee that this technique is a science. Therefore, analyzing and discussing Psychoanalysis as a science is an aspect of the highest complexity, because what Freud achieved was the creation of a technique and, while he was improving it, he had to develop an entire methodology that would provide epistemological support to the therapeutic-clinical method he adopted. In this, he found himself at a crossroads, having to choose between the epistemological development of his therapeutic technique or to focus on it as an investigative science.

It so happened that Freud was developing an innovative and revolutionary technique and along with it came the lack of content that would help professionals practice Psychoanalysis. The solitude to which he was subjected in the early years of his career both helped him and exacerbated his rigid stance regarding his technique.

Freud had to deepen his epistemological search, inducing, deducing, producing ideas, developing hypotheses, and testing them until they were strengthened as valid theories and could be presented to the general public. Much of what Psychoanalysis contributed to the various areas of human knowledge was produced by its own investigative search in the clinical field, starting from the need to understand its object of study and from there, interpret its behavior, both in isolation and as a whole.

Taking this scope of analysis into account, one can come to the conclusion that the complexity of defining Psychoanalysis as a science or as a technique alone is due to the effort that its creator had to make to ensure that it had technical/theoretical support material, as well as scientific production that would give it a didactic-academic character. All of this was achieved and became possible, in fact, due to Freud's singular effort on behalf of his treatment technique applied to patients suffering from neuroses.

Thinking about a technique linearly, like a natural science, is an action that cannot be directed or executed, simply by defining whether it is or is not a certain thing, evaluating it in a contingent manner. Even after the entire range of theoretical material already produced around Psychoanalysis and the entire technical process that makes it possible to infer about the objects of study, helping in the understanding of facts and phenomena, it is still not enough to obtain the *status quo* of a science, because this would require, in addition to a specific method and a specific methodology, more plausible relationships between cause and effect, which would allow its validation by third parties. However, "Freud's epistemological virtue, on the contrary, seems to have been his willingness to allow his conception of science to change as his research progressed, without prejudice to his conviction that it remained within the boundaries of the natural sciences" (SIMANKE, 2009, p. 233).

Freud was a very strict thinker in his scientific convictions and understood his role in the field of science as an act of exploration and endless challenges, to which he could relate to his thinking and his object of study, which was, beyond the human being, an instance that, in addition to being inside the human being, somewhere in his brain, was unknown as to its power of action and how it responded to the effects caused by existence. Remaining tied to the principles of natural sciences was a risk to take; but his anger against philosophy, which fought

so that its technique would not be seen as such, was what kept him tied to this idea and this ideal.

It is strange that Sigmund was concerned that his technique would be compared to an existential philosophy. With Psychoanalysis, life and existence are not explained; they are merely analyzed, approaching facts and phenomena in an interpretation that makes them more transparent and understandable to the majority. With this, it has been possible to offer better living conditions to patients and even to others who have applied the knowledge derived from it to their respective lives without going through the couch of an analyst. Paradoxically, its use as a way of explaining human reality occurs in academic circles and not among the general population, where it tends to be better accepted and treated more seriously, even if there is no mastery over the psychological processes that encompass it, in a more or less profound way, depending on the level of neurosis that affects the individual. Based on the knowledge acquired through its application to the most complex cases, human behavior has become a peaceful object to be understood and comprehended, helping many individuals to find a solution to their intra and extra psychic conflicts.

In this sense, the relationship between psychoanalysis and science is as a means through which one is able to achieve a specific end and that, without this instrument, one would tend to find explanations in superstitions and other types of allegories. The explanation that it gives to human phenomena and their manifestation can be understood as loaded with allegorical elements, at first glance; however, a more detailed analysis reveals that a whole myriad of ontogenetic and phylogenetic elements are expressed until reaching the singular characteristic expressed in human existential reality.

Science tends to reduce everything to the individual and the simple, so that it can study each case in isolation, while psychoanalysis, even when dealing with isolated individuals, cannot dissociate all the elements of the human being, having to carry out its interpretation based on a set of data that are always interconnected. Freud knew this very well and, despite his struggle to have his technique recognized as a science, this concept must be interpreted in the Master's thinking, which was something very specific in relation to his practice.

CONCLUSION

Discussing the relationship between Psychoanalysis and science is, in itself, a very broad and complex issue; because, on the one hand, there are instances in which the technique has been applied to an object, which are nervous patients (neurotics), and on the other hand,

there is an entire scientific-literary production that has revolutionized the ways of thinking about existence and human life, in [*almost*] every sense, influencing a range of other fields of knowledge, as well as other sciences and their clinical activities. However, all this apparatus and the entire collection surrounding Psychoanalysis is not enough to place it at the center of the sciences or classify it as such.

Paradoxically , the results achieved through its clinical application end up categorizing it as a science, which raises the challenge of thinking about the direct contributions it has provided over time. This is because the method used by Psychoanalysis, even when it seeks to conduct in-depth investigations, is very unreliable in terms of being able to perform analyses and interpretations in order to validate what has been discovered, through the spontaneous speech of patients. These only reveal [*or deny*] their feelings, traumas and conflicts, leaving it up to the analyst to uncover the truth that remains hidden by the patient himself, to the extent that he cannot or is unable to confront it directly. This understanding that is reached, after extensive studies, is the closest to a paradigm about it that can be achieved.

Based on this paradigm, it is concluded that Psychoanalysis is a technique that, when applied correctly, in an organized and systematic manner, produces excellent therapeutic healing results and these, once compiled in the records, serve as guidance guides, enabling a broad understanding of the social object with which social sciences deal, which is the human being.

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